

STUDIES IN CHALKONES. PART I. CHALKONES DERIVED FROM RESACETOPHENONE AND ITS DIMETHYL ETHER.

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Resacetophenone dimethyl ether has been condensed with *o*-vanillin, isovanillin, 5- and 6-methoxysalicylaldehyde, and resacetophenone with *o*-vanillin to yield corresponding hydroxymethoxychalkones. Attempt has been made to determine the optimum condition for these condensations.

On account of the fact that the resorcinol nucleus occurs in the vast group of natural flavone, isoflavone, flavonol and chalkone colouring matters, it would appear to be of interest to synthesise compounds of this type. The most easily synthesised are the chalkones, a few of which have been prepared by previous workers by condensation of resacetophenone and its mono- and dimethyl ethers with aldehydes (Perkin and Hummel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 1459; Perkin, Robinson and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 1109; Göschke and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 3502, 1912, **45**, 186; Bargellini and Lydia Monti, *Gazzetta*, 1914, *ii*, **44**, 25; Tambor, *Ber.*, 1916, **49**, 1704; Shinoda, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1928, **48**, 214; Shinoda, Sato and Kawangoe, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1929, **49**, 123; Hattori, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1932, **6**, 131; Russell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 218; Mahal, Rai and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 866; Saiyad, Nadkarni and Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1737; Nadkarni and Wheeler, *ibid.*, 1938, 1320).

In the present communication resacetophenone dimethyl ether has been condensed with *ortho*-vanillin, 5- and 6-methoxysalicylaldehyde, and with isovanillin and resacetophenone with *ortho*-vanillin, giving the corresponding hydroxymethoxychalkones. An attempt has also been made to determine the optimum conditions for condensing resacetophenone and its dimethyl ether with some aldehydes in order to obtain the maximum possible yields of the chalkones, specially in view of the fact that the reaction is reversible (*cf.* Schriner and Kurosawa, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2538), the equilibrium being dependent on the concentration of alkali and on the temperature, these two conditions varying within wide limits from one chalkone to another.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pure resacetophenone was prepared by the following modification of

the original method due to Nencki and Sieder (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1881, 23, 147). Fused zinc chloride (55 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (60 g.), freshly distilled over fused sodium acetate, and dry resorcinol (40 g.) added and the mixture heated on the sand-bath until the temperature of the mixture was 144° when the heating was discontinued. Robinson and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1494) by treating the cold reaction mixture with a mixture of equal volumes of concentrated hydrochloric acid and water obtained moderately pure resacetophenone, m. p. 133-140° (yield 91%), while the present author obtained 72% of resacetophenone, m. p. 144-45°, by crystallising the product from hot water.

Methyl alcohol used in the following condensations was freed from traces of formaldehyde by distillation over silver nitrate.

2:4-Dimethoxyphenyl-3'-hydroxy-4'-methoxystyryl ketone.—(a) A mixture of resacetophenone dimethyl ether (3.2 g.), isovanillin (2.5 g.), methyl alcohol (10 c. c.) and 30% methyl alcoholic caustic potash (10 c. c.) was heated to boiling on the water-bath, when the mixture quickly became deep red. After keeping at 50-60° for 24 hours, the mixture was diluted with water, boiled to remove methyl alcohol, and extracted with ether to remove any unchanged resacetophenone dimethyl ether. The viscous precipitate obtained on acidification with dilute acetic acid was washed with water and thrice crystallised from small quantities of hot alcohol in lemon-yellow stout prismatic needles, m. p. 115°, yield 3.9 g. (73.6%). (Found : C, 68.8 ; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.8 ; H, 5.7 per cent).

It is readily soluble in cold methyl and ethyl alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, benzene, chloroform, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride, and less so in ether and petroleum ether. It dissolves in alkalis to a deep yellow or orange-red solution, and with concentrated sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid gives a deep orange red colouration; but there is no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

(b) A mixture of resacetophenone dimethyl ether (3.6 g.), isovanillin (3 g.) methyl alcohol (20 c.c.) and 25% methyl alcoholic caustic potash (50 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 1 hour when it quickly became bright red, but no precipitate separated. After keeping for 12 hours at 40-45°, the red solution was diluted with water and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid giving a yellow crystalline precipitate of the chalkone (5.5 g; 88.7%).

2 : 4-Dimethoxyphenyl- 2'- hydroxy- 6'- methoxystyrylketone.—(a) A mixture of resacetophenone dimethyl ether (3.6 g.), 6'-methoxysalicyl aldehyde (3 g.), methyl alcohol (30 c. c.) and 50% aqueous caustic potash (20 c. c.) was heated to boiling on the water-bath for 10 minutes

and then kept at 50-55° for 24 hours, when a bulky red precipitate of the potassium derivative of the chalkone separated. It was filtered, washed with a little methyl alcohol and its aqueous solution acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, when a lemon-yellow precipitate (5.1 g. and 0.2 g.) on acidification (after dilution) of the filtrate from the potassium salt was obtained. It was crystallised once from dilute ethyl alcohol (greenish yellow prisms), twice from hot benzene and finally from ethyl acetate as yellow leaflets or plates, m. p. 116.5°. (Found in sample dried at 80° under high vacuum: C, 68.7; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.8; H, 5.7 per cent). It is fairly soluble in all organic solvents in the cold. It gives a deep red colouration with concentrated sulphuric and hydrochloric acid and an intense green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The results of other experiments are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Caustic potash.	Duration of heating on the water-bath.	Kept at	Yield.
20 C. c. of 50% aq.	10 min.	50-55° for 24 hr.	5.3 g. (82.3%)
40 C. c. of 40% methyl alcoholic	20	50° „ 12	3.4 g. (55.8%)
40 C. c. of 25% „ „	30	50° „ 12	2.6 g. (41.9%)
30 C. c. of 25% „ „	30	20-22° „ 24	2.3 g. (37.0%)

2:4-Dimethoxyphenyl-2'-hydroxy-3'-methoxystyrylketone.—A mixture of resacetophenone dimethyl ether (3.6 g.), *o*-vanillin (3 g.), methyl alcohol (20 c.c.) and 50% aqueous caustic potash (20 c.c.) was heated for 10 minutes on the water-bath, when the potassium derivative of the chalkone separated as bulky glistening red needles. The mixture was then kept at 50-55° for 24 hours. The potassium salt was filtered and decomposed in aqueous suspension with dilute hydrochloric acid. The dried lemon-yellow crystalline product (4.9 g., 79.6%) was recrystallised from boiling alcohol as bright yellow prisms, m.p. 117°. (Found in sample dried at 80° in high vacuum: C, 68.6; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.8; H, 5.7 per cent). It is moderately soluble in cold ethyl and methyl alcohol and ethyl acetate, and sparingly in cold benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether and petroleum ether. It gives a deep red colouration with sulphuric and hydrochloric acid, and with alcoholic ferric chloride, a green colouration.

The results of other experiments are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Caustic potash.	Duration of heating on the water-bath.	Kept at	Yield.
20 C.c. of 50% aq.	10 min.	50-55° for 24 hr.	4.9 g. (79.6%)
40 C.c. of 25% methyl alcoholic	20	50-55° for 12	5.4 g. (87.0%)
50 C.c. of 40% methyl alcoholic	20	50° for 12	4.8 g. (75.13%)

2 : 4-Dimethoxyphenyl-2'-hydroxy-5'-methoxystyrylketone.—A mixture of resacetophenone dimethyl ether (3.6 g.), 5-methoxysalicylaldehyde (3 g.), methyl alcohol (30 c.c.) and 50% aqueous caustic potash (20 c.c.) was heated for 10 minutes on the water-bath and then kept at 50–60° for 12 hours. The bulky red crystalline precipitate of the potassium salt was filtered, washed with a little alcohol, dissolved in water and acidified; the orange-yellow precipitate was washed and dried (5.1 g., 82.2%). It crystallised from aqueous alcohol and also from benzene as brownish yellow needles, m.p. 129°. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.8; H, 5.7 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold methyl and ethyl alcohol and ethyl acetate and slightly in benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, petroleum ether and ether. It gives with concentrated sulphuric and hydrochloric acid a cherry-red colouration and none with alcoholic ferric chloride.

2 : 4-Dihydroxyphenyl-2'-hydroxy-3'-methoxystyrylketone.—A mixture of resacetophenone (3 g.), *ortho*-vanillin (3 g.), methyl alcohol (40 c.c.) and 50% aqueous caustic potash (40 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath at 60-65° for 24 hours, when it became deep red in colour and the red potassium derivative of the condensation product crystallised out. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and treated with dilute acetic acid giving a gummy yellow mass, which solidified and crumbled to a fine yellow powder on standing. It was filtered, well washed and dried. The filtrate from the potassium salt similarly gave the chalkone (yield 3.6 g., 63.8%). The acid filtrate on concentration gave a dirty white crystalline substance (1 g.) which is under examination.

The chalkone was dissolved in the minimum amount of hot methyl alcohol and water added to slight turbidity, when it separated as tiny bright yellow needles, the mother-liquor on concentration yielding more of the substance. It was recrystallised from alcohol as bright yellow needles, m.p. 211°. (Found in sample dried at 100°: C, 67.0; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 67.1; H, 4.49 per cent).

It is readily soluble in cold ethyl and methyl alcohol, moderately so in ethyl acetate, and almost insoluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, petroleum ether and ether. Concentrated sulphuric acid gives a cherry-red colouration, and hydrochloric acid none in the cold, but a red colouration on warming, and alcoholic ferric chloride, a dark greenish brown colouration.

The results of other experiments are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III.

Caustic potash.	Duration of heating on the water-bath.	Kept at		Yield.
40 C.c. of 50% aq.	0 hr.	60-65°	for 24 hr.	3.6 g. (63.8%)
60 C.c. of 25% methyl alcoholic	0	60°	24	4.5 g. (83.3%)
40 C.c. of 25% methyl alcoholic	4	20-22°	24	1.1 g. (19.5%)
60 C.c. of 25% methyl alcoholic	2	20-22°	24	2.15 g. (35.2%)

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